

Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂) Assay Kit Instruction

1. Principle of Measurement

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) can form a coordination complex with molybdate which can be detected by recording the absorbance at 405nm. Upon this, the amount of hydrogen peroxide can be determined.

2. Reagent Compositions and Preparation

Reagent I: 1 Bottle×60ml. Stored at 4 ° C and is stable for 6 months.

Reagent II: 1 Bottle×60ml. Preserved at 4 ° C for 6 months. As a supersaturated solution, crystallization may occur and under such circumstance, dissolve the crystal at 60 ° C.

H₂O₂ Stock Solution: 1 Bottle × 5ml. Preserved at 4 ° C for 6 months.

Preparation of 163 μ M H₂O₂ Standard Solution: Dilute the stock solution with double distilled water (DDW) with the ratio 1:9 (v/v) right before use.

3. Procedures

Compositions (ml)	Blank	Standard	Sample
Reagent I (Pre-warm at 37 ° C)	1	1	1
DDW	0.1		
H ₂ O ₂ Standard Solution		0.1	
Sample			0.1
Reagent II	1	1	1

Blend the mixture and regulate the spectrophotometer with DDW. Record the absorbed optical density (OD) at 405 nm.

4. Notes

- I. Reagent I should be pre-warm at 37 ° C for 10 min before use.
- II. Pre-test should be done before measurement. Were the OD values exceeds 0.8 or below 0.05, decrease or increase the amount of samples accordingly and the amount of standard solution and DDW added should be adjusted as well.

5. Calculation Formula and Examples

I. Serum Samples

a. Formula

$$H_2O_2 \text{ Content}_{\mu\text{M}} = \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{Standard}}}{163\mu\text{M}} \times \text{Coefficient of Dilution}$$

b. Example

Extracted bovine serum 0.1 ml for measurement and the OD values for blank, standard and sample tubes were 0.006, 0.341 and 0.099 respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} H_2O_2 \text{ Content}_{\mu\text{M}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{Standard}}}{163\mu\text{M}} \times \text{Coefficient of Dilution} \\ &= \frac{0.099 - 0.006}{0.341 - 0.006} \times 163\mu\text{M} \times 1 = 45.25\mu\text{M} \end{aligned}$$

II. Tissue Samples

a. Formula

$$H_2O_2 \text{ Content}_{\mu\text{M}} = \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{Standard}}}{163\mu\text{M}} \div \frac{\text{Protein Content}}{\text{g/L}}$$

b. Example

10% rat lung tissue homogenate 0.1ml was extracted and measured and OD values were 0.008, 0.346 and 0.065 respectively. Also, the protein content was measured as 6.284g/L for the homogenate.

$$\begin{aligned} H_2O_2 \text{ Content}_{\mu\text{M}} &= \frac{OD_{\text{Sample}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}}{OD_{\text{Standard}} - OD_{\text{Blank}}} \times \frac{C_{\text{Standard}}}{163\mu\text{M}} \div \frac{\text{Protein Content}}{\text{g/L}} \\ &= \frac{0.065 - 0.008}{0.346 - 0.008} \times 163\mu\text{M} \div 6.284\text{g/L} = 4.03\mu\text{mol/g} \end{aligned}$$